

A Clinical Comparison between the Standard Macintosh and the Trupti Laryngoscope Blade for Laryngeal Visualization in Anaesthetised AdultsVijay S. Shah¹, Dipeshkumar P. Shah², Maulik Mehta³¹Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, SAL Institute of Medical Sciences, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, SAL Institute of Medical Sciences, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India³Department of Anaesthesia, SAL Institute of Medical Sciences, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Difficult airway may be encountered in both anticipated and unanticipated circumstances. Difficult laryngoscopy and failed intubation result in severe morbidity related to anaesthesia. This has forced the anaesthesiologists to pursue their interest in developing newer gadgets to facilitate successful and safe endotracheal intubation. One such gadget is the levering laryngoscope blade. We conducted a clinical trial to compare the usefulness of Trupti blade with Standard Macintosh blade for providing glottic view, for endotracheal intubation.

Methods: We included 235 patients belonging to ASA I and II, of either Sex, between 18-70 years, undergoing elective surgery and requiring endotracheal intubation.

Results: We found that, the incidence of difficult laryngoscopy with Standard Macintosh was 7.66% compared to 0.85% with Trupti blade in Elevated position. Trupti blade in Elevated position significantly improved restricted glottic view when compared with Standard Macintosh blade. However, in Neutral position the Trupti blade provided less grade I and II and more grade III and IV views when compared to Standard Macintosh blade, suggesting worsening of glottic view.

Conclusions: The Trupti blade in elevated position significantly improved the glottic views during difficult laryngoscopy in comparison with Standard Macintosh blade. However, in Neutral position Trupti blade did not behave identical to the Standard Macintosh blade and made the glottic view worse. The Trupti blade may be added to the armamentarium of aids to difficult intubation available in the operation theatre as well as in ambulances.

Keywords: Difficult Airway, Trupti Blade, Standard Macintosh Blade, Glottic View.

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Introduction

Nature constantly challenges anaesthesiologist's theoretical knowledge, practical skills and decision-making power. "The Difficult Airway" is the situation when he needs these skills at its best. The airway management is a fundamental aspect for practice of anaesthesiology, emergency and critical care medicine. Endotracheal intubation is a rapid, simple, safe and non-surgical technique that achieves all the goals of airway management; namely, maintains airway patency, protects the lungs from aspiration and permits leak free ventilation during mechanical ventilation. It remains the gold standard procedure for airway management.

Inability to view the larynx adequately during laryngoscopy is a major problem encountered during endotracheal intubation. The difficult

tracheal intubation accounts for 17% of the respiratory related injuries and results in significant morbidity and mortality. In fact up to 28% of all anaesthesia related deaths are secondary to the inability to mask ventilate or intubate. [1] This has forced the anaesthesiologists to encourage development of newer gadgets as well as modification of current instruments to achieve successful and safe endotracheal intubation. Range of instruments available for endotracheal intubation varies from simple direct laryngoscope blade to complex fiberoptic laryngoscope. To improve effectiveness of standard Macintosh laryngoscope blade, it has been modified to various types. One such modification by McCoy and Mirakhor is Levering Laryngoscope Blade (LLB) [2]. It offers the unique advantage of a hinged blade tip, controlled by a lever on the handle of the

laryngoscope, allowing elevation of the epiglottis and improves the visualization glottis.

An Indian Company, Anaesthetics (Bombay) have manufactured a LLB, named the "TRUPTI" blade, having exactly similar hinged tip design like McCoy Blade. During difficult endotracheal intubation with a Macintosh laryngoscope, the application of increased lifting force combined with a levering movement of the blade is inevitable. In this case, the patient is exposed to potential damage, and the upper teeth may be inadvertently used as a fulcrum [3]. The engineering design of the McCoy levering laryngoscope was one of the first attempts to address these difficulties. Having its fulcrum at a lower point within the pharynx, it was expected to simplify the elevation of the epiglottis and the exposure of the larynx, reducing contact with the upper incisor teeth. [4] This will facilitate the anaesthesiologist in performing safe and successful endotracheal intubation in difficult laryngoscopy.

After Janeway performed tracheal cannulation first time with battery powered open side laryngoscope in 1913, over sixty types of laryngoscope blades have been developed and studied but only few are widely used in clinical practice. [5] Since its introduction in 1993 the LLB has gained popularity with positive results in many clinical studies but literature search did not yield many studies evaluating effectiveness of "TRUPTI" blade. Hence, it is imperative to subject this newer gadget to thorough scientific evaluation regarding its usefulness in difficult laryngoscopy and safe endotracheal intubation on the bases of many studies done on McCoy blade.

Previous studies have compared laryngoscopic visualization with Macintosh blade, McCoy Blade in Neutral and in Elevated position in each patient so that exact evaluation of laryngeal visualization can be done. Based on such studies we have also done laryngoscopy by both blades in each patient. We studied and compared the effectiveness of Standard Macintosh Blade and Trupti Blade in neutral and elevated positions, for visualization of laryngeal structure in anaesthetised adults.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining Institutional ethical committee approval and written informed consent from the patients, the study was conducted on 235 ASA I and II patients. This study followed a prospective, randomized, double blind design and the study was done during February 2008 to January 2009 at SAL hospital and medical institute, Ahmedabad.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria: Patients of either sex with age between 18-70 years, belonging to ASA grade I and II, those undergoing elective

surgery, in whom endotracheal intubation was indicated were included in the study.

Patients with upper respiratory tract infections, Patients who were at risk of pulmonary aspiration of gastric contents, History of cervical spine pathology were excluded from the study.

Sample size calculation: In a study done by Harioka T. et al., the authors compared Macintosh and McCoy blade in neutral and elevated position with or without external laryngeal pressure in 219 patients. They observed that the McCoy blade improves glottis exposure, so that grade III and IV views by Macintosh blade, improved to grade I or II with blade tip elevation in 63% of patients. [6]

Taking into account of the above observations the sample size of 235 was calculated using formula, Sample Size (n) = $4pq/L^2$.

Here positive predictive value (p) was considered 63%, negative predictive value (q) is 37% (100-p) and allowable error (L) was kept at 10% of positive predictive value. [7]

Statistical Analysis: The McNemar's chi square test (a test of paired proportions) was used to these 2 x 2 tables for comparison of two blades. P value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Procedure: On arrival of the patients to the operating theatre, an appropriate intravenous line was secured and patients were positioned in the "sniffing" position with a 10 cm firm standardized foam pillow under their head.

Monitoring consisting of electrocardiography, non-invasive arterial blood pressure, pulse oximetry and peripheral nerve stimulation of the ulnar nerve at the wrist attached.

Laryngoscopy was performed by the investigators who have considerable experience in the use of the Trupti laryngoscope blade.

Patients were, Preoxygenated with 100% oxygen for 5 minutes, Premedication with intravenous Inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.005 mg/kg and inj. Midazolam 0.05 mg/kg. Patients were induced with inj. Fentanyl 2 mcg/kg. + Inj. Propofol 2 mg/kg and Suxamethonium 2 mg/kg of body weight. Patients' lungs were ventilated manually via a facemask with 100% oxygen until muscle paralysis is complete as shown by no twitches from a train-of-four stimulus. The laryngoscopy was performed twice using a Macintosh laryngoscope blade (size 4), and Trupti laryngoscope blade (size 4) in a random sequence. (The sequence was randomized according to a computer-generated list. Best glottic view were noted based on Cormack Lehane scoring of grade I to IV, for the Standard Macintosh Laryngoscope and the Trupti Laryngoscope blade in Neutral and Elevated position. Endotracheal

intubation was accomplished with the blade which was used latter. In case of worsening of glottic view with the latter blade, then the other blade was used to accomplish endotracheal intubation and whenever necessary, external laryngeal pressure, e.g., backward, upward, and to the right pressure (BURP) and devices assisting intubation (e.g., gum elastic bougie) were used to facilitate intubation. Anaesthesia was continued as per requirement of the specific surgery.

Parameters assessed: The Cormack Lehane grading of glottic views on laryngoscopy with,

1. The Standard Macintosh blade,

2. Trupty blade - Neutral position,
3. Trupty blade - Elevated position.

Results

The study was conducted to compare the effectiveness of Trupty blade in neutral and elevated positions for improvement in visualization of glottis in comparison with Standard Macintosh blade. 235 patients, aged between 18-70 years, of either sex, belonging to ASA class I and II, scheduled to undergo elective surgery under general anaesthesia and to whom endotracheal intubation was indicated, were enrolled in this prospective study.

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Parameters

Sr No.	Parameters	Value			
1	Age (Mean \pm SD) years	45.21 \pm 15.35			
2	Sex (M:F)	119:116			
3	TMD (Mean \pm SD) cm	6.42 \pm 0.76			
4	Mallampatti Classification (Number of cases/percentage)	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV
		80	113	26	16
		34.05%	48.08%	11.06%	6.81%

Out of 235 patients, 119 (50.64%) were males and 116 (49.36%) were females. The mean age of participants was 45.21 \pm 15.35 years with mean thyro- mental distance of 6.42 \pm 0.76 cm. All above findings were not statically significant to affect the final outcome of the study. Out of 235 patients,

34.05% patients had Mallampatti grade I, 48.08% patients had Mallampatti classification grade II, 11.06% had grade III while 6.81% were with grade IV. These percentages of MP grading are comparable to data collected in other study done by Radha et al. on 39,058 patients. [8]

Table 2: Comparison of Glottic Views with Standard Macintosh, Trupty Blade in Neutral and In Elevated Position

Sr. No.	Laryngoscope blades	Glottic views				
		Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV	Total
1	Standard Macintosh	75	142	18	0	235
2	Trupty blade- Neutral position	16	127	92	0	235
3	Trupty blade- elevated position	163	70	2	0	235

The percentage of easy glottic views grade I & II in Standard Macintosh blade was 31.91% & 60.43% respectively, where as in Trupty elevated position it was 69.36% & 29.79% respectively.

And the percentage of restricted glottic views (grade III) in Standard Macintosh blade and Trupty in elevated position was 7.66% and 0.85% respectively. Grade IV view was not observed in

any blades. However, the percentage of Grade I view in Trupty blade in neutral position was only 6.81%, which was lower when compared to Standard Macintosh blade and Trupty blade in elevated position, the percentage of restricted glottic view was also higher (39.15%), when compared to Macintosh blade and Trupty blade in elevated position.

Table 3: Comparison of Glottic Views with Standard Macintosh Blade and Trupty in Neutral Position

	Glottic View	Trupty Neutral position		
		Grade I & II	Grade III & IV	Total
Standard Macintosh	Grade I & II	143	74	217
	Grade III & IV	0	18	18
	Total	143	92	235

As shown in the TABLE 3 out of 217 patients who had Grade I & II with standard Macintosh blade, only 143 patients had Grade I & II and 74 patients

had Grade III & IV with Trupty blade in Neutral position.

None of the patient who had Grade I & II with Trupty blade in Neutral position had Grade III & IV with standard Macintosh blade. 74 out of 92 patients (Grade III & IV with Trupty blade in Neutral position) were observed to be Grade I & II with standard Macintosh blade. 18 patients had Grade III & IV with both blades.

On applying McNemar Chi-square test of proportions, with 1 degree of freedom to TABLE 3, Chi-square value is 72.01. Hence according to chi

square table, McNemar Test $P = 0.000$ (p Value < 0.05 considered statistically significant). There was a significant difference between Standard Macintosh blade & Trupty Blade in neutral position. Standard Macintosh blade had higher Grade I & II views and lower Grade III & IV views when compared to Trupty Blade in neutral position. Standard Macintosh blade proved superior in providing more number of easy glottic view and less number of restricted glottic views when comparison with Trupty Blade in neutral position.

Table 4: Comparison of Glottic Views with Standard Macintosh Blade and Trupty in Elevated Position.

	Glottic View	Trupty - Elevated position		Total
		Grade I & II	Grade III & IV	
Standard Macintosh	Grade I & II	215	2	217
	Grade III & IV	18	0	18
	Total	233	2	235

As Shown in the TABLE 4, Trupty blade in Elevated position obtained 233 grade I & II, out of that in 18 patients laryngoscopic view was inferior with Standard Macintosh blade.

On applying McNemar Chi-square test of proportions, with 1 degree of freedom to TABLE 4.

χ^2 value is 14.45. Hence according to chi square table McNemar test $P = 0.0001$ (p Value < 0.05 considered statistically significant)

There was a significant difference between Standard Macintosh blade & Trupty Blade in elevated position. The Trupty Blade in elevated

position could reduce the difficult laryngoscopic views from 18 to 2 when compared to the Standard Macintosh blade. This was statistically significant ($P = 0.0001$).

The Trupty Blade converted all 18 grade III views by Standard Macintosh blade to easy glottic views. 14 out of these 18 cases were predicted difficult intubation by M.P.G. classification and T.M.D. However in 2 cases Standard Macintosh blade obtained superior glottic view compared to grade III view by Trupty Blade in elevated position, interestingly both of these cases were predicted to be easy intubation.

Table 5: Comparison of Glottic Views with Trupty in Neutral Position and Trupty in Elevated Position.

	Glottic View	Trupty - Elevated position		Total
		Grade I & II	Grade III & IV	
Trupty Neutral position	Grade I & II	143	0	143
	Grade III & IV	90	2	92
	Total	233	2	235

As per TABLE 5, 90 out of 92 patients who had grade III & IV were converted to grade I & II on activation of lever with Trupty blade. In 2 patients glottic view did not improved after activation of lever. Among 233 patients who had easy glottic view (Grade I & II) with elevated tip, 90 patients had restricted glottic view (Grade III & IV) before elevation of tip with Trupty blade.

On applying McNemar Chi-square test of proportions, with 1 degree of freedom to TABLE 3, χ^2 value is 92.01. Hence according to chi square table McNemar test $P = 0.000$ (p Value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant) Numbers of difficult laryngoscopic views (Grade III & IV) in Trupty blade Neutral position were 92 compared to just 2 when the levering mechanism was activated. This difference was statistically highly significant ($P < 0.001$). Trupty blade in

Elevated position significantly reduced restricted glottic views when compared to neutral position. Overall, Trupty Blade in elevated position proved superior to Standard Macintosh blade. However, Standard Macintosh blade was better than Trupty Blade in neutral position.

Discussion

Difficult visualization of the larynx (DVL) was defined by the ASA task force as situation when it is not possible to visualize any part of the vocal cords by conventional laryngoscopy. [9] Endotracheal intubation is a common anaesthetic procedure usually accomplished with ease. However, when it proves difficult, the patients' life may be threatened. The incidence of DVL has been reported to be between 1.5 to 13%, that of difficult intubation to be 1 to 4% and failed intubation between 0.1 to 0.3%. [9] A closed claim analysis

showed that most common cause of morbidity in such cases was hypoxia caused by inadequate ventilation, resulting from difficult tracheal intubation or accidental esophageal intubation. In 85% of these cases, the outcome was death or brain damage. [9] The incidence of DVL in our study was 7.66% and this result was in concordance with the study which reported an incidence of 1.5 to 8.5%. [10] Wide variations in the incidence of DVL can be ascribed to various factors such as lack of uniformity in describing or grading laryngeal views, application of cricoid pressure, head positioning during laryngoscopy, degree of muscle relaxation and type or size of laryngoscope blade used. This variation can be noted in our study as the incidence of DVL with Trupty blade elevated position was only 0.85% when compared to 7.66% with Standard Macintosh blade (TABLE 2).

Several preoperative airway assessment tests have been proposed to predict DVL, such as modified Mallampati test (MMT), thyromental distance (TMD), sternomental distance (SMD), horizontal length of the mandible (HLM) and inter incisors gap (IIG). These tests have been used singly or in various combinations in the past. However, they are characterized by low sensitivity, reasonable specificity and low positive predictive value. They all have significant false positive results. [11]

The investigators in a study observed that MPG was the most useful single predictor of DVL with a sensitivity, specificity and positive predictive value of 61.5%, 98.4% and 57.1% respectively. [12] MPG shows more significance with conventional laryngoscopy. Authors in a study found a 33% incidence of difficult laryngoscopy with the Macintosh blade as compared to only 5% with the McCoy LLB. [13]

The Trupty blade in the neutral position provided more Grade II (127) and fewer Grade I (16) of glottic views compared to the Macintosh blade (142 and 75 respectively) (TABLE 2). When paired views in individual patients were compared, the Trupty blade in neutral position made the view worse ($p < 0.05$) (TABLE 3). Trupty blade in elevated position proved significantly superior to the Macintosh blade in improving Grade III or IV glottic views to Grade I or II ($p < 0.05$) (TABLE 4). Trupty blade in elevated position proved better than Trupty in neutral position ($p < 0.05$) and the Standard Macintosh blade ($p < 0.05$) in providing glottic view for endotracheal intubation (TABLE 4 and D).

In a previous study of comparison between the Macintosh and the McCoy laryngoscope blades, it was observed that McCoy blade in neutral position provided the worst view. This was in concordance with our results. However, in the same study, the glottic views between McCoy elevated position and the Macintosh blades failed to show much

significance, instead both were comparable. [14] This was in contrast to the significant difference observed between the two in our study. We think this difference observed may be because of the smaller sample size used in above study.

In a previous study, authors used LLB in selected patients who had thyroid swellings. [15] These patients were expected to pose increased incidence of difficult laryngoscopy. LLB proved highly useful in these patients; however, LLB did not obviate the need of BURP manoeuvre to improve glottic view. In our study we used BURP manoeuvre to improve glottic view in difficult laryngoscopic views to facilitate endotracheal intubation. The Trupty blade was designed to elevate the epiglottis with its hinged tip.

This unique design had two advantages when compared with the Macintosh laryngoscope blade. First, use of the Trupty blade resulted in less force being applied during laryngoscopy and the stress response to laryngoscopy was significantly reduced. [16] Secondly, difficult laryngeal visualization might be improved by lifting epiglottis, especially in patients with the neck fixed in the neutral position. It was observed that McCoy LLB could improve glottic exposure, in 83% of patients who had difficult laryngoscopy with the Macintosh blade. In them Grade III views improved to Grade I or II on elevation of the distal tip of LLB. [13] In a similar study, difficult laryngoscopy was encountered in 26 out of 102 patients using the McCoy LLB in neutral position. Of these 26 patients, 24(92%) had glottic structures identified (Grade I or II) when the distal tip of the laryngoscope blade was activated. This was a significant improvement ($p < 0.001$). [17]

In our study in 18 out of 235 patients, difficult laryngoscopy was encountered with the Macintosh Blade. Of these, all 18 patients had glottic structures identified with the Trupty blade in elevated position. This was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$) improvement. The high incidence of DVL in the previous study (72%) 13 when compared with our study (7.66%) was because of the simulation of difficult intubation by manual in line stabilization of the neck in that study group.

Why LLB in its neutral position does not behave identical to the Macintosh blade, which it closely resembles? Is it because of the inability to blind the observer to the use of the blade? We agree with the previous study where it was opined that such observation was because of the inability to blind the observer to the use of the blade. Knowing that levering could improve the view, the investigators might not have tried manoeuvres such as controlled increased force to obtain the best view in neutral position. [18] Another author opined that this

behaviour could have been caused by the slight change noted between the tips of McCoy LLB and the Macintosh Blade. [19] Trupti blade's shape is somewhat in between the straight blade and the curved blade.

The long axis of spatula is straight near the base and towards tip distal 1/3rd length is curved. Whether such difference could cause a significant change is questionable.

Some studies have reported improvements while the others have reported deterioration of the laryngeal view with the activation of the levering mechanism of the McCoy LLB. Even in our study, we observed deterioration of laryngeal view in two cases. In them easy glottic view was obtained with the standard Macintosh blade but Grade III view with Trupti blade in elevated position. Even though this was statistically not significant, has lot of clinical implications. Endotracheal intubation was accomplished with standard Macintosh blade in these patients.

This behaviour of LLB has prompted various investigators to reject the recommendations of the inventors of LLB that it can be used as the first choice for routine laryngoscopy. [14] We agree with the authors of a previous study in recommending the addition of Trupti blade to the armamentarium of aids to difficult intubation available in the theatre suite.

However, should not replace the Macintosh blade in routine laryngoscopy as the first choice. The investigators conducted a laryngoscopic imaging study with the McCoy LLB and concluded that the variable effects of LLB on activation could be explained by the effective pivot position of the blade with activation of the levering mechanism. Worsening of laryngeal view was due to the downward movement of the middle portion of the blade into the line of sight. [20]

In another study the authors considered the reason for worsening of glottic view on activation of lever especially when the glottis is widely seen, is the result of the elevation of the glottis together with the epiglottis. [21] A mechanical failure of the lever mechanism of McCoy LLB during the course of intubation of what was suspected to be a difficult intubation has been reported. [22]

This was due to the breakage of braze that connects the proximal pivot of the lever mechanism to the blade itself. However, no such complications were noticed in our study. In order to prevent such complications in future, we recommend compulsory checking of the levering mechanism prior to laryngoscopy with LLB.

Our experience with this new LLB indicates that it was useful in a substantial proportion of patients who were Grade III view with standard Macintosh

laryngoscopy. We feel that it should be available as an aid to difficult intubation, especially in conjunction with the gum elastic bougie.

Limitations

The observer could not be blinded to the use of the blade for laryngoscopy. In our study, Grade II glottic views obtained with Trupti blade in elevated position had better glottic exposure than the grade II views obtained with the Standard Macintosh blade. However, this could not be documented with Cormack and Lehane grading system. Hence further evaluation of Trupti blade using POGO score (Percentage of Glottic opening) would be more appropriate. [23]

Conclusion

From the present study we concluded that: 'TRUPTI' a new levering laryngoscope blade was useful in improving the glottic view, in elevated position when compared with the Standard Macintosh blade, for accomplishing endotracheal intubation.

However, in neutral position Trupti Blade made the glottic view worse when compared with the Standard Macintosh blade. Trupti Blade in neutral position did not behave identical to the Standard Macintosh blade.

The Trupti Blade was useful in substantial proportion of patients who were Grade III view on laryngoscopy. The Trupti Blade may be added to the armamentarium of difficult intubation trolley available in the operation theatre.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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